

1 **OX40 ligation results in activation of TNFSF15, the ligand for death receptor 3 (DR3), induction of**
2 **BCL2 family members BCL2, BCL2L2, BCOR, and BAG5 concomitant with activation of the**
3 **Fas-related molecule FAIM.**

4 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

5 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

6 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

7 East Islip, NY USA 11730

8 Exhaustion receptors include members of the TNF superfamily like OX40, encoded by TNFSF15. The
9 transcriptional consequences of OX40 ligation at the cell surface are incompletely understood; currently,
10 monoclonal antibodies targeting exhaustion receptors are approved for the medical treatment of solid
11 tumors include PD1 and PD-L1; monoclonal antibodies targeting TIGIT are currently in late-stage trials for
12 cancer including non small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and pharmacologic agonism and antagonism of
13 OX40 is currently in development. We studied total transcription following experimental ligation of OX40
14 to describe cellular output associated with transduction of OX40 signals with an agonist. We observed
15 TNFSF15 activation concomitant with caspase-4 induction and repression of caspase-2 and caspase-9 in
16 regulatory T cells following administration of an OX40 agonist in mouse and man. TNFSF15 activation
17 occurred concomitant with BCL2 family induction. The chemokine CKLF and the morphogen receptor
18 BMPR2 were activated. OX40 ligation exerted control of lymphocyte-specific signal transduction: ITK was
19 induced, but FYN and LYN were repressed. PDCD4 was activated in OX40 ligated cells, together with
20 modulation of THEMIS, and activation of LAG3. STIM1 was transcriptionally induced. In the nucleus,
21 TBX22 was activated following OX40 ligation concomitant with induction of TAF5I and SS1811. OX40
22 ligation was further characterized by a widespread proteasomal activation event and modulation of
23 cytokines as well multiple interferons and interferon stimulated genes (ISGs) that together function as
24 components of the senescence pathway. OX40 agonism is associated with a unique profile of cellular
25 output and transcriptional changes featured by a "mixed" set of changes in cell death signaling, control of
26 inflammatory and exhaustion-related immune signaling.
27
28